

Modelling and Power Quality Investigation of Grid Connected PV Inverter with Active and Reactive Power Mode using Decoupled PQ Theory

Venkatasamy B^{#1}, Kalaivani L^{*2}

^{#*}Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, National Engineering College, Kovilpatti, Tamilnadu, India

Abstract— A comprehensive look at alternative energy sources is necessary to meet the current demand for power since fossil fuel resources are being utilized quickly. World Energy Outlook 2023 states that the global energy market will continue to grow rapidly from clean energy resources like solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind. The solar PV inverter is a key component of the solar energy system. The two primary types of inverters are grid-connected inverters and standalone inverters. Reactive power-capable grid-connected PV inverters are among the most recent developments in the solar power sector. This paper has examined a grid-connected PV inverter's reactive power capabilities. This work's key objective is to develop an improved controller with higher performance for active and reactive power abilities for a solar photovoltaic double-stage inverter. Furthermore, the primary goal of the work is to analyze the grid-connected PV inverter's performance and power quality in both active and reactive power generation modes. Comparing the grid-connected inverter with the classical feed-forward approach, decoupled P-Q theory-based control using a PI controller gives insightful conclusions and findings.

Keywords— Grid-connected Inverter - Solar Photovoltaic System - Reactive Power Mode - Renewable Energy Generation -PV Energy System

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to the deficiency of fossil fuels and the decreased cost of producing PV power, consumers are now encouraged to use solar power. Solar PV systems are being used to generate electricity, which is then delivered to the utility grid for public use. The downsides of PV systems, such as more installation costs and lower power conversion efficiency, deter people from using PV energy. Developments in power electronics technologies thus lead to enhanced system efficiency and new opportunities for using photovoltaic energy in various applications. Technological advancements have also made the system usage of various converter control schemes feasible. In addition to these functions, these converters provide active and reactive power, regulate voltage, and maximize the output from the PV module or array [1].

The technique of drawing the maximum possible power from the photovoltaic source is known as maximum power point tracking. An inverter and boost converter are the two components of a two-stage PV system, while the PV inverter uses the MPPT directly in the former [2]. The single-stage PV systems have benefits over two-stage systems, owing to the absence of a boost converter. Still, because of the unreliable solar irradiance, the DC-link voltage fluctuates more at the inverter's input, which makes handling the MPPT and keeping the DC-link voltage more challenging. A two-stage system comprising MPPT control with an intermediate boost converter (IBC) was designed to satisfy the grid-connected inverter's required input DC voltage level [3]. Researchers have suggested a variety of MPPT control techniques to regulate MPP. Solar PV panels, power converters, and additional ancillary modules, including filters, transformers, and additional system components, are commonly found in grid-connected photovoltaic systems. DC/DC and DC/AC converters are examples of converters with a power electronics basis.

II. OVERVIEW OF GRID-CONNECTED INVERTERS

Unlike off-grid PV installations, grid-connected PV systems operate synchronously with the electrical utility grid, negating storage device requirements. The grid requires only expressly active power, but in some circumstances, it also requires either positive or negative reactive power to maintain voltage stability and regulation [4]. Reactive power functionality has recently been added to inverters, allowing them to inject both active and reactive power dependent on the user reference value set [5]. Furthermore, if solar radiation is unavailable, these kinds of inverters can inject reactive power only (i.e., at night).

This mode of operation is known as VAR mode; in VAR mode, the PV inverter functions as STATCOM, injecting reactive power alone based on its reference or requirement and using minimal active power from the grid. Transformer and transfer-less topologies are the other essential topologies used in PV inverters. Line frequency transformers are employed for power voltage matching to prevent DC injection into the grid, which also offers galvanic isolation between the inverter and the grid [6]. However, line frequency transformers are not economical due to their large size and weight. In light of this disadvantage, several topologies are presented, such as a high-frequency transformer integrated into the DC-to-DC conversion [7].

Transformer-less solar PV inverters obtained attention due to their reduced costs, lighter weight, and increased efficiency. An H6 transformer-less full-bridge grid-connected solar PV inverter is used in the suggested reactive power modulation with the grid current distortion improvement method [8]. Although transformer-less topologies are a more affordable option for photovoltaic systems, most inverter manufacturers still employ transformer architecture due to the significant disadvantage of limited output voltage range, which lowers overall efficiency. However, due to evident zero-crossing current distortion and DC injection, the H6 transformer-less topology with traditional control techniques and modulation may not guarantee the requirement for reactive power compensation [9]. Therefore, Space Vector Pulse Width Modulation (SVPWM), in contrast to traditional switching modulation, provided a novel reactive power capability [10]. Likewise, a variety of topologies, including Space Vector Pulse Width Modulation, current-mode asynchronous sigma-delta modulation, and simplified reactive power control, are employed in the grid-connected PV inverter for active/reactive power injection mode for the power quality studies [11].

Recent advances have highlighted the necessity for reactive power support for grid-connected PV inverters to facilitate grid voltage regulation, VAR mode, and other features. According to Jianhua Wang et al. [12], phase shift in the current reference and straightforward switching pattern modifications enable reactive power generation capabilities with lower zero-crossing distortion. According to recent studies, more research is necessary to determine the inverter's power quality in both active and reactive power modes and a possible solution. Even though many topologies are suggested in the literature, little research has been done on the inverter's power [13].

The inverter's controlling methods, such as power injection, stability, power quality, etc., govern the grid-connected PV system's overall performance. The three main categories of inverter controllers are intelligent, nonlinear, and linear [14]. Feed-forward control using the d-q theory was presented as a linear control method to manage active and reactive power injection independently and provide the quality output current under investigation [15]. These classical PI controllers are considered based on the system's characteristics and dynamics. Researchers have demonstrated that adoptive p-q theory combined with a PI controller can enhance power quality (THD) in shunt active filters [16]. The PI controllers are traditionally employed to generate the necessary output power because of their simplified construction. This study examines the performance of grid-connected photovoltaic inverters utilizing various controllers, comprising feed-forward controllers that use d-q theory and hysteresis controllers that use adaptive p-q theory [17]. This proposed work aims to investigate the performance parameters of a 75kW solar PV system that can produce both active and reactive power using these controllers.

III.NEED OF REACTIVE POWER

In the power triangle shown in Figure 1, an angle θ is created by the inductive load absorbing reactive power (Negative Q). A high angle reduces the power factor ($\text{Cos}\theta$), increasing the voltage drop and load current and decreasing grid voltage regulation. Reactive power injection (Positive Q) is required to mitigate the reactive power consumption. This reactive power injection increases load current, improves grid control, and decreases the angle as θ' (i.e., increases power factor), Reactive power compensation should consistently be implemented locally to get maximum power from the grid.

Fig. 1 Power Triangle

Fig. 2 Change in Grid voltage to Power Factor

Reactive power consumption (Lagging PF) of the inductive load contributes to the decrease in the grid voltage profile. Figure 2 illustrates how reactive power injection, or leading, enhances the grid voltage. The electrical utility's local reactive power consumption must always be balanced to maintain a steady voltage on the grid. A capacitor bank or FACTS device is frequently employed to compensate for this reactive power. It will be exciting to see the existing grid-connected inverters functioning in reactive power generation mode when there is no active power output [18]. The grid-connected inverters can generate reactive power by applying a suitable phase shift of the current angle with the grid voltage.

IV. CONTROL SCHEME FOR THE GRID CONNECTED INVERTER

Here, two kinds of inverter control schemes are discussed: their control theory pros and cons, experimental results, and valid discussions.

A. Feed-Forward Controller Using D-Q Theory

The system configuration of the grid-connected 75kWp solar PV system is shown in Figure 3. Here, a 76kW PV array is being used. A DC-DC boost-type converter is used for MPPT to implement an incremental conductance approach.

Fig. 3 Control scheme for the grid-connected inverter with Feed Forward Controller

A voltage source inverter with SPWM converts the photovoltaic power into AC power. A distribution transformer connects the PV inverter's output to the grid. The parallel RC and serial RL can be used for

sine filters. IEEE33 bus distribution makes use of a utility grid. A 76kW PV array is built using the PV array block that comes with MATLAB Simulink. The number of series and parallel strings is adjusted to obtain the required power and voltage.

B. Maximum Power Point Tracking Control

The efficiency of a solar PV system is decreased when variables like temperature, irradiance, and fluctuating PV voltages prevent a PV array from producing its full potential power. A PV array can only generate maximum power at a particular voltage. Additionally, the voltage will change continuously based on the circumstances. The voltage at which the highest power can be extracted is monitored by the MPPT controller. The basic MPPT algorithm is perturb and observe algorithm and this algorithm's drawback is that it won't be able to follow or respond to a sudden change in the environmental condition [19]. The incremental conductance technique is used in this proposed study to overcome this issue. Equations (1) and (3) determine the maximum power point tracking according to the characteristics of the incremental conductance approach [20].

$$\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V} = -\frac{I}{V}, \text{ at MPP} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V} > -\frac{I}{V}, \text{ Left side of MPP} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V} < -\frac{I}{V}, \text{ Right Side of MPP} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 4 Incremental Conductance Algorithms for Maximum Power Point Tracking

Inverter Control schemes

The three-phase voltage on the secondary side of the transformer (HV) will be transformed to the per-unit system as per equation (4).

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_a \\ v_b \\ v_c \end{bmatrix}_{meas} = v \begin{bmatrix} \sin \omega t \\ \sin(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3}) \\ \sin(\omega t + \frac{2\pi}{3}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Three-phase vectors "abc" can be mathematically converted into two-phase vectors d-q. For the d-q transformation, the signals are assumed to be straight lines under steady-state circumstances. Every interruption in the three-phase AC system will likewise cause disruptions to the DC d-q components. The system's analysis and control are made easier by the synchronous rotating frame (d-q) [21]. Equation (5.5)

provides the relationship between the measured three-phase voltage's abc and d-q. Similarly, in the d-q reference frame, the transformer's three-phase current is supplied by equation (5.6).

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_d \\ v_q \\ v_0 \end{bmatrix}_{meas} = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} \sin\omega t & \sin(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3}) & \sin(\omega t + \frac{2\pi}{3}) \\ \cos\omega t & \cos(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3}) & \cos(\omega t + \frac{2\pi}{3}) \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_a \\ v_b \\ v_c \end{bmatrix}_{meas} \tag{5}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_d \\ I_q \\ I_0 \end{bmatrix}_{meas} = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} \sin\omega t & \sin(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3}) & \sin(\omega t + \frac{2\pi}{3}) \\ \cos\omega t & \cos(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3}) & \cos(\omega t + \frac{2\pi}{3}) \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_a \\ I_b \\ I_c \end{bmatrix}_{meas} \tag{6}$$

The transformation matrix yields the direct and quadrature components' values of the measured voltage and currents $V_d, meas, V_q, meas, I_d, meas, I_q, meas$. The active power reference, $I_{d,ref}$, is found using the error signal of $V_{dc,meas}, V_{dc,ref}$, and PI Controller. Equation (7) illustrates how the voltage and current measurements are used to calculate the active power reference.

$$I_{d,ref} = k_p(V_{dc,meas} - V_{dc,ref}) + k_i \int (V_{dc,meas} - V_{dc,ref}) dt \tag{7}$$

Because it depends on grid requirements, the active power reference, or $I_{d,ref}$, is obtained from the observed value to the common point of connection to the grid. Reactive power consumption is a feature that many inverters now provide, nevertheless. When power is injected at the unity power factor, the reactive power reference is usually set to zero. Whenever reactive power is required for the grid, the $I_{q,ref}$ value can be adjusted from -1 to +1 (i.e., the inverter is to be operated in VAR mode at a lagging/leading power factor). Equations 8 and 9 provide the output of the feed-forward current controller, which generates sinusoidal PWM signals for the VSI.

$$v_{d,conv} = \mu_d - L\omega I_{q,ref} + RI_{d,ref} + V_{d,meas} \tag{8}$$

$$v_{q,conv} = \mu_q - L\omega I_{d,ref} + RI_{q,ref} + V_{q,meas} \tag{9}$$

C. Hysteresis Controller using Adoptive PQ theory.

The suggested system layout for the three-phase grid-connected PV system is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5 Schematic of Proposed Configuration with SPV System

It has an MPPT DC-DC boost converter, an SPV, a utility grid, a filter, and a PV inverter. A boost converter's output terminal maintains the DC-Link voltage. The boost converter uses the maximum power that the photovoltaic system can provide as an input to deliver a regulated output to the DC-Link. Using the INC MPPT technology, the maximum amount of solar power is harvested, as before. The voltage and current grid measurements are transformed into d-q and provided to the suggested controller. The controller generates an error signal after obtaining the actual and PQ values. Finally, a VSC with hysteresis control creates the sinusoidal power supply. RC filter circuits in series and parallel provide the desired sinusoidal output voltage. The distribution transformer is linked to the inverter's output terminals to deliver power to the grid. The utility grid uses the IEEE33 bus distribution network to validate the findings.

Inverter Control Methodology

Because the system's transient conditions grow increasingly difficult to evaluate the harmonics, each phase should be independently managed during design. These issues are resolved mathematically by converting the three-phase vector "abc" into the two-phase vector d-q [22]. The suggested controller provides the reactive and active references before converting again into "abc" to provide a hysteresis controller. The hysteresis controller generates the gating pulses of the inverter.

Fig. 6 Decoupled P-Q control for Grid-tied PV inverter

The decoupled P-Q theory divides active and reactive power in the inner loop [23], [24]. Figure 6 illustrates the decoupled P-Q control of the Grid-tied PV inverter. Park's transformation can compute the real and reactive power using equations (10) and (11).

$$P = 1.5(V_{od} * i_{od} + V_{oq} * i_{oq}) \tag{10}$$

$$Q = 1.5(V_{od} * i_{od} - V_{oq} * i_{oq}) \tag{11}$$

Where, the d-q coordinates $V_{od}, i_{od}, V_{oq}, i_{oq}$ indicate the voltage and current of the grid. Consequently, the proposed inner loop eliminates the short circuit current transients. In addition, a hysteresis voltage controller has been employed to lower grid current distortion (THD) and improve power quality.

V. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

This paper investigates the reactive power capability and current THD of a grid-connected 75kW photovoltaic inverter. The results of the proposed system are validated with the MATLAB Simulink platform. The proposed system comprises the Voltage Source Converter (VSC) with a hysteresis controller, an IEEE 33 distribution that serves as a grid, a DC-DC Boost converter, and an SPV Array. Solar irradiation delivers power to the DC-DC converter with incremental conductance MPPT, providing the most electrical power in various ecological circumstances. The stability of the power system is improved when a DC-to-DC converter with boost topology raises the voltage level while keeping the DC link voltage constant. The voltage source inverter (VSC) is controlled using a hysteresis controller and

decoupled P-Q theory. A filter circuit is connected between the distribution transformer and the VSC to provide a sinusoidal output. In the proposed study, different controllers independently control the reactive and active power. The authors disclose the power quality study using the feed-forward controller [25]. The system uses decoupled PQ theory with a hysteresis controller to assess and compare with the feed-forward controller.

A. Experimental Results of Feed-Forward Controller

Fig.7 (a) Solar PV system's per-phase output voltage (HV side) (b) Output current per-phase (HV Side) (c) (d) Output voltage and current THD with feed forward control (e) VSI output voltage (f) Output of both reactive and active to the grid

Experimental Results for a grid-connected PV inverter with a Feed-Forward Controller using the d-q theory are shown. Figure 7 depicts the active/reactive output power to the grid for a reactive power reference of 0% ($I_{q,ref} = 0$) and the per-phase output voltage, current, and THD plot of the corresponding voltage and current. The current controller produces the active power reference $I_{d,ref}$ by the grid requirements (100%). THD for this reference is 0.14%, the current THD is 2.56%, the equivalent current at the HV side is 5.86A, and the RMS phase voltage is 6.04kV. At the unity power factor roughly, the active power output is 67.96 kW, and the positive reactive power is 256.68 VAR.

B. Experimental Results using Hysteresis Controller using PQ Theory

The reference values are given individually for reactive power control injection and absorption. In this instance, active power is maintained constant, but reactive power can change. The controller's feed-forward and hysteresis control the reactive and active power output. In other words, the reference value of reactive power is changed from 75 kVAR to 15 kVAR while constant active power is employed. Only reactive power is managed by the feed-forward control system; the active power reference is left unchanged, and the current THD at the 15kVAR reference is roughly 2.46%. The study uses decoupled P-Q theory with a PI controller to reduce the current THD and regulate the power.

Fig. 8 (a) Output voltage THD with proposed controller in reactive power mode (b) Output voltage THD with proposed controller during UPF (c) Output current THD with proposed controller in reactive power mode (d) Output voltage THD with proposed controller during UPF

The study demonstrates that in various operating modes, the current THD of the suggested system remains within the upper limit of 1.87%. In contrast, the feed forward controller (FFC) has a maximum of 2.56% at UPF. Figure 8 shows the current THD analysis of the reference values with reactive power injection and absorption and at UPF with hysteresis current controller.

An inverter requires a maximum of active power and zero reactive power to achieve a UPF state. With a current THD of 2.76%, the UPF condition active power is 67.96kW, and the reactive power is 0.25kVAR in the typical feed-forward approach. However, active power is 74.81kW with a current THD of 1.87% in decoupled P-Q theory with PI controller utilization. Also, the study inferred that the current THD at UPF is somewhat elevated compared to the injection and absorption of reactive power.

The Active and reactive power output and its corresponding voltage THD and current THD for the various reactive power references are tabulated in Table 1. The PI with hysteresis controller using decoupled PQ theory performed well from the simulation outcomes. Its reactive power output is closer to reference, and its current distortion (THD) is low compared to Feed Forward with SPWM using d-q theory.

Table 1 Controllers Performance and THD analysis with reactive power absorption, injection, and UPF

Reactive Power Reference	Absorption of Reactive Power (Q- Negative)									
	Feed Forward with SPWM					PI with Hysteresis Controller				
	Active power (kW)	Reactive power (kVAR)	Power Factor	Voltage THD (%)	Current THD (%)	Active power (kW)	Reactive power (kVAR)	Power Factor	Voltage THD (%)	Current THD (%)
75	67.13	-64.72	0.72	0.13	1.79	74.87	-67.57	0.72	0.11	0.87
60	67.46	-51.78	0.79	0.13	1.98	74.87	-54.85	0.79	0.11	0.95
37.5	67.69	-32.29	0.9	0.13	2.25	74.92	-34.01	0.91	0.11	1.13
15	67.98	-12.8	0.98	0.14	2.46	75.23	-13.41	0.99	0.11	1.57
Injection of Reactive Power (Q- Negative)										
-75	67.58	65.5	0.72	0.15	2.07	74.37	69.8	0.71	0.11	0.92
-60	67.66	52.44	0.79	0.15	2.23	74.01	54.21	0.78	0.11	1.37
-37.5	68.17	33.01	0.9	0.15	2.46	73.87	34.94	0.89	0.11	1.64
-15	68.03	13.36	0.98	0.14	2.54	73.51	13.71	0.98	0.11	1.72
Unity Power Factor (Q = 0)										
0	67.96	0.25	1	0.14	2.76	74.81	0.32	1	0.12	1.87

VI. CONCLUSIONS

A study is carried out on a 75kW grid-connected solar photovoltaic system. During the day, the solar PV inverter's active and reactive power capabilities are being studied. The MATLAB Simulink platform is used to model the PV energy system, and its many properties have been analyzed. The grid voltage increases by reactive power injection and decreases by positive reactive power mode. When it's necessary to regulate the voltage on the local grid, the reactive power mode can be helpful. An investigation of power quality has been carried out in the PV inverter using both modes. The voltage THD value consistently stays within allowed bounds (0.15%). The present THD value in the injection/reactive power consumption mode is within the 2.76% range. Moreover, based on the simulation results, the harmonics depend on the harmonic order of the fifth harmonics alone. Compared to feed forward with SPWM using d-q theory, the PI with hysteresis controller utilizing decoupled PQ theory performed well; its reactive power output is closer to reference, and its current distortion (THD) is low.

REFERENCES

- Libo, W, Zhengming, Z & Jianzheng, 'A single-stage three-phase grid-connected photovoltaic system with modified MPPT method and reactive power compensation', *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 881-886, 2007.
- Jain, S & Agarwal, V, 'A single-stage grid connected inverter topology for solar PV systems with maximum power point tracking', *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 22, no. 5, pp. 1928-1940, 2007.
- Kamran Zeb, Waqar Uddin, Muhammad Adil Khan, Zunaib Ali, Muhammad Umair Ali, Nicholas Christofides & Kim, HJ, 'A comprehensive review on inverter topologies and control strategies for grid-connected photovoltaic system', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 94, pp. 1120-1141, 2018.
- Varma, RK & Siavashi, EM, 'Enhancement of solar farm connectivity with smart PV inverter PV-STATCOM', *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 1161-1171, 2019.
- Kamran Zeb, Waqar Uddin, Muhammad Adil Khan, Zunaib Ali, Muhammad Umair Ali, Nicholas Christofides & Kim, HJ, 'A comprehensive review on inverter topologies and control strategies for grid-connected photovoltaic system', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 94, pp. 1120-1141, 2018.
- Yan, Q, Wu, X, Yuan, X, Geng, Y & Zhang, Q, 'Minimization of the DC component in transformerless three-phase grid-connected photovoltaic inverters', *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 30, no. 7, pp. 3984-3997, 2015.
- Yang, B, Li, W, Gu, Y, Cui, W & He, X, 'Improved transformerless inverter with common-mode leakage current elimination for a photovoltaic grid-connected power system', *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 752-762, 2012.

8. Zhang, L, Sun, K, Xing, Y, Feng, L & Ge, H, 'A modular grid-connected photovoltaic generation system based on DC bus', *IEEE Transaction on Power Electronics*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 523-531, 2011.
9. Ji, B, Wang, J & Zhao, J, 'High-efficiency single-phase transformerless PV H6 Inverter with Hybrid Modulation Method', *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol.60, no.5, pp. 2104-2115, 2013.
10. Keliang, Z, Danwei, W, Bin, Z & Yigang, W, 'Plug-in dual-mode-structure repetitive controller for CVCF PWM inverters', *IEEE Transaction on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 56, no.3, pp. 784-791, 2009.
11. Wu, TF, Chang, CH, Lin, LC & Kuo, CL, 'Power loss comparison of single- and two-stage grid-connected photovoltaic systems', *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol.26, no.2, pp. 707-715, 2011.
12. Jianhua Wang, Fangfang Luo, Zhendong Ji, Yichao Sun, Baojian Ji, Wei Gu & Jianfeng Zhao, 'An improved hybrid modulation method for the single-phase H6 inverter with reactive power compensation', *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 33, no. 9, pp. 7674-7683, 2018.
13. Kamran Zeb, Waqar Uddin, Muhammad Adil Khan, Zunaib Ali, Muhammad Umair Ali, Nicholas Christofides & Kim, HJ, 'A comprehensive review on inverter topologies and control strategies for grid-connected photovoltaic system', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 94, pp. 1120-1141, 2018.
14. Karimi-Ghartemani, M & Iravani, MR, 'A method for synchronization of power electronic converters in polluted and variable-frequency environments', *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 1263-1270, 2004.
15. Aditi Chatterjee & Kanungo Barada Mohanty, 'Current control strategies for single phase grid integrated inverters for photovoltaic applications-a review', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 92, pp. 554-569, 2018.
16. Karuppanan, P & Kamala Kanta Mahapatra, 'PI and fuzzy logic controllers for shunt active power filter - A report', *ISA Transactions*, vol. 51, no. 1, pp.163-169, 2012.
17. Georgios Tsengenes & Georgios Adamidis, 'Investigation of the behaviour of a three-phase grid-connected photovoltaic system to control active and reactive power', *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 81, no. 1, pp. 177-184, 2011.
18. Jianhua Wang, Fangfang Luo, Zhendong Ji, Yichao Sun, Baojian Ji, Wei Gu & Jianfeng Zhao, 'An improved hybrid modulation method for the single-phase H6 inverter with reactive power compensation', *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 33, no. 9, pp. 7674-7683, 2018.
19. Elkhateb, A, Rahim, NA, Selvaraj, J & Uddin, MN, 'Fuzzy- logic-controller-based SEPIC converter for maximum power point tracking', *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 50, no. 4, pp. 2349-2358, 2014.
20. Sivakumar, P & Arutchelvi, M 2017, 'Maximum power extractions in a single stage PV sourced grid-connected inverter during low irradianations and nonlinear loads', *Renewable Energy*, vol. 107, pp. 262-270
21. Mohan Lal Kolhe & Rasul, MJMA, '3-Phase grid-connected is building integrated photovoltaic system with reactive power control capability', *Renewable Energy*, vol. 154, pp.1065-1075, 2020.
22. Mahmud, MA, Hossain, MJ, Pota, HR & Roy, NK, 'Robust nonlinear controller design for three-phase grid-connected photovoltaic systems under structured uncertainties', in *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 1221-1230, 2014.
23. Ivanqui, J, Voltolini, H, Carlson, R & Watanabe, EH, 'pq theory-control applied to wind turbine trapezoidal PMSG under symmetrical fault', *Proceedings of International Electric Machines & Drives Conference*, pp. 534-540, 2013.
24. Teodorescu, R, Blaabjerg, F, Liserre, M & Loh, PC, 'Proportional-resonant controllers and filters for grid-connected voltage-source converters', *IEEE Electric Power Applications*, vol. 153, no. 5, pp. 750-762, 2006.
25. Venkatasamy, B & Kalavani, L, 'Modeling and power quality analysis of grid-connected PV inverter with active and reactive power injection mode', *Journal of Electrical Engineering and Technology*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 1375-1387, 2021.